

RFSS based on Cross Dipole or Grid using PIN Diode

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ABSTRACT: This work presents an RFSS with two discrete states, corresponding to a pass-band or stop-band response depending on PIN diode biasing. The RFSS behaves as an array of cross dipole elements when all diodes are in the OFF-state and as a grid when the diodes are in the ON-state. The cross dipole patch array has a stop-band filter response and the grid behaves as a pass-band filter at the design frequency of 1.6 GHz. Simulation and measurements of insertion loss are presented, demonstrating the switchable band-pass to band-stop response.

Keywords: Frequency Selective Surface, Reconfigurable Device, RFSS, AFSS, PIN Diode.

1. INTRODUCTION

Typically, Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSS) are two-dimensional periodic arrays that behave as spatial filters [1]. The frequency response of an FSS will behave as a stop-band if the single element of the array is a patch. Analogously, an aperture array element will result in a pass-band response [2]. Variables such as unit cell geometry, dimension and periodicity are important factors for determining the FSS frequency response [3].

An extension of the FSS is the Reconfigurable Frequency Selective Surfaces (RFSS). RFSS properties (such as resonant frequency and polarization) can be changed in real time, while passive FSS has constant characteristics. The ability to vary the frequency response can be achieved by introducing active elements into the device, such as the PIN diode [4], which is commonly used as a switch. PIN diodes are placed as switches along the RFSS structure to provide reconfiguration. An external DC bias is applied to the diodes as forward or reverse bias to define the ON or OFF state of the PIN diodes, respectively. When a diode is forward biased, it creates a new path for current flow, which results in changes over the FSS's response. MEMS [5], varactors [6] and photodiodes [7] can also be used to reconfigure devices.

This paper presents a RFSS whose array consists of cross dipoles connected by PIN diodes. By changing the state of the diodes, the RFSS's frequency response can be toggled between stop band and pass band. Both configurations operate in dual TE/TM polarization for an orthogonal incident angle. The simulation was held using CST Microwave Studio 2016[®]. Simulated and measurement results for insertion loss are presented here.

2. CROSS DIPOLE – GRID RFSS

A. Structure

A cross dipole is shown in Figure 1 (a). The cross dipole resonates when its length is a half-wavelength [8]. An FSS whose elements are cross dipoles is expected to have a stop-band characteristic response, since the cross dipoles behave like patches. Another possible FSS configuration is the grid configuration, shown in Figure 1 (b). This time, the FSS unit cell is a grid expected to produce a pass-band response, since its structure is composed by apertures.

The key to achieving the proposed RFSS structure, relies on PIN diode placement at the edge of the cross dipoles, as illustrated in Figure 1 (c). Notice that when the diodes are in OFF state, there is no current flowing between the cross dipoles. Therefore, the RFSS will behave as a cross dipole FSS (stop-band). However when the diodes are in ON state current flows through the dipoles. Consequently, the RFSS will behave as a grid FSS (pass-band). This simple configuration is remarkably interesting because of its simplicity and also because it allows FSS reconfiguration by a change of filtering function (i.e. toggling between pass-band and stop-band responses).

B. Circuit bias

The RFSS contains an array of $N \times N$ diodes. The cross dipoles are connected to each other by diodes placed at their edges. By choosing the appropriate diode orientation (see Figure 2) it is possible to switch all diodes with just two DC bias points in the structure (GND and V_{cc}). The diodes are connected in an orientation that goes from lower voltage to higher voltage, or vice versa, as shown in the Figure 2. The diodes are forward biased or reverse biased, all at once. In order to simplify simulations, the ON-state diode is replaced by a conducting printed strip on the substrate connecting the cross dipoles. Alternatively,

the OFF-state diode is represented by a spacing between the cross dipoles, even though this model does not account for diode intrinsic properties, such as resistance and reactance, it provides a first approximation and allows demonstrating the reconfigurable band-pass to stop-band RFSS concept.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the measured and simulated results for the proposed RFSS considering a normal incidence of a vertically polarized plane wave. The simulation of the structure considering open and short circuits replacing the diodes is shown in Figure 3. The center frequency occurs at 2.21 GHz with S_{21} values of -29 dB for the OFF-state and -0.6 dB for the ON-state, successfully demonstrating the stop-band and pass-band responses of the device, respectively.

In order to validate the simulations, a 4x4 array (i.e. 16 unit cells) version of the RFSS was fabricated as shown in Figure 4. The periodicity of the unit cell is 46.5 mm, the length and width of the cross dipole are 45.5 mm and 1 mm respectively. The substrate used was FR-4 ($h=1$ mm, $\epsilon_r=4.4$, $\tan\delta=0.02$). An array of 24 diodes (Infineon's BAR64) is used. The experimental results are obtained using an Agilent E5071C Vector Network Analyzer and two SAS-571 double ridge guide horn antennas. The measurement setup includes a panel with a slot of 20cm x 20cm to hold the FSS, shown in Figure 5. Absorbers are used to prevent undesired reflection. The dimensions of the RFSS are 18.5 cm x 18.5 cm. A square copper loop was made around the FSS to provide bias to the diodes and to fill in the slot. The loop was sectioned into two parts, one to provide V_{cc} and other connected to GND.

Two types of measurement were performed. The first measurement verifies S_{21} as a function of V_{cc} , varying from 0 to 5 Volts, shown in Figure 6. For values of V_{cc} from 0 to

3 V, the RFSS behaves as a stop band filter. For values of V_{cc} above 4 V, the RFSS behaves as a pass band filter. The second-measurement verifies the behavior of the RFSS for values of V_{cc} from -5 to 0 Volts. As shown in Figure 7, there is no apparent change in frequency response when the V_{cc} is below 0V.

Experimental measurements show that when the diodes are in ON-state ($V_{cc} = 5V$) the RFSS behaves as a pass-band ($S_{21} = -4dB$ at 1.63GHz). When the diodes are in OFF-state ($V_{cc} = 0V$) the RFSS behaves as a stop-band ($S_{21} = -15dB$ at 1.63GHz). Table 1 presents a comparison between simulated and measured insertion loss. A frequency shift between the simulated and measured results occurred due to the parasitic elements of the diodes.

5. CONCLUSIONS

As shown in both simulated and measured results, the RFSS performs as expected, changing filtering characteristic when its diodes are toggled between ON and OFF states. Experimental and simulated results show a good agreement and demonstrate the versatility of the structure as a reconfigurable filter. However, a shift between experimental and simulated results is presented. This is believed to be due to the use of an ideal short circuit as a model for the diode ON-state. The RFSS behaves as a band-pass filter when the diodes are at ON-state. At OFF state, the RFSS behaves as a band-stop filter. Switching V_{cc} between 0 V and 5 V is sufficient to change the filtering characteristic of the RFSS, therefore, the structure can be controlled by ordinary low-power circuits. This structure can be applicable for devices such as adaptive and RFID antennas.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Huang, T.-K. Wu e S.-W. Lee, “Tri-band frequency selective surface with circular ring elements”. *Antennas and Propagation, IEEE Transactions on*, pp. vol.42, no.2, pp.166-175, Feb 1994. [1]
- [2] A. L. P. S. Campos, “Superfícies seletivas em frequência: análise e projeto”. Natal: IFRN Editora, 2009. [2]
- [3] J. Bossard, D. Werner, T. Mayer e R. P. Drupp, “A novel design methodology for reconfigurable frequency selective surfaces using genetic algorithms”. *Antennas and Propagation, IEEE Transactions on*, pp. vol.53, no.4, pp.1390-1400, April 2005. [3]
- [4] T. Chang, R. Langley e E. Parker, “An Active Square Loop Frequency Selective Surface”. *Microwave and Guided Wave Letters, IEEE*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp.387-388, october 1993. [4]
- [5] L. Fengrong, W. Ting, “Design of reconfigurable UWB microstrip antenna with MEMS switches”, *IEEE International Conference on Microwave and Millimeter Wave Technology (ICMMT)*, Vol. 2, pp.740 – 742, 2016.
- [6] J. Yuan, S. Liu, X. Kong e H. Yang, “A reconfigurable frequency selective surface for tuning multi-band frequency response separately”. *Antennas & Propagation (ISAP), Proceedings of the International Symposium on*, pp. Vol. 02, Pages: 1288 – 1290, Oct 2013. [6]
- [7] W. M. Dorsey, C. S. McDermitt, F. Bucholtz, M. G. Parent, “ Design and Performance of Frequency Selective Surface With Integrated Photodiodes for Photonic Calibration of Phased Array Antennas”, *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, Vol. 58, pp. 2588 - 2593, 2010.

- [8] J. Bossard, D. Werner, T. Mayer e R. P. Drupp, “A novel design methodology for reconfigurable frequency selective surfaces using genetic algorithms”. *Antennas and Propagation, IEEE Transactions on*, pp. vol.53, no.4, pp.1390-1400, April 2005. [8]

Table 1 Data from measured and simulated insertion loss.

	f_{01} (GHz)	Attenuation (dB)	Central Frequency (GHz)	Attenuation (dB)	f_{02} (GHz)	Attenuation (dB)
Meas	1.50	-10,00	1,63	-15	1,8	-10,00
Sim	2.08	-10,00	2.23	-29	2.37	-10,00

Figure 1 FSS's Unit Cells: (a) Cross dipole element; (b) Grid element; (c) Cross dipoles connected by diodes.

Figure 2 Diodes' orientations: from Vcc to GND.

Figure 3 Manufactured RFSS with 24 PIN Diodes.

Figure 4 S_{21} simulated results for RFSS (replacing the diode for an ideal strip).

Figure 5 Measurement setup for the RFSS.

Figure 6 S_{21} as a function of V_{cc} ($V_{cc} > 0V$).

Figure 7 S_{21} as a function of V_{cc} ($V_{cc} < 0V$).